

Heterogeneous Redox Polymerisation of Vinyl Acetate in Aqueous Medium

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The results of the aqueous polymerisation of vinyl acetate, initiated by $K_2S_2O_8 - Na_2S_2O_4$ system, indicate: (i) the rate rises with the persulphate concentration to a maximum and then falls, tending to rise again at higher concentrations of the persulphate; (ii) the rate is continuously retarded as the hydrosulphite concentration is increased; (iii) the rate is linear in monomer up to a certain concentration of the latter, beyond which it falls; (iv) added salts retard the rate; (v) initiators, added at the start of polymerisation, enhance the rate, but when added later, retard the rate; (vi) the variation of the rate, aquo-sol stability, and intrinsic viscosity is parallel; (vii) intrinsic viscosity increases with time in a run. These features have been explained from the points of view of the theory of Smith and Ewart.

Previous communications¹⁻⁴ of this series reported the kinetics of the heterophase aqueous polymerisation of monomers, such as methyl methacrylate¹⁻⁴, acrylonitrile^{2,4}, and methyl acrylate³, using potassium persulphate and sodium hydrosulphite as the redox initiator. The present communication describes the same for vinyl acetate.

The emulsion and aqueous polymerisation of vinyl acetate have received lately some attention⁵⁻⁹. The results can, however, hardly be fitted into any particular kinetic model of the theory of Smith and Ewart¹⁰; moreover, some of the reported experimental facts are contradictory^{8,11}. More recently, Napper and Parts¹²⁻¹³ report that their results on the persulphate-initiated aqueous polymerisation of vinyl acetate more or less conform to case III of the theory of Smith and Ewart, i.e., polymerisation in large-size suspended polymer particles attended with intraparticle gel-effect.

We have already discussed¹⁻⁴ the influence of the stability of the physical state of the polymers on the kinetics of such heterogeneous polymerisation processes. The results of the present investigation have been examined from this viewpoint and the conditions under which case III of Smith-Ewart's kinetic model is likely to prevail have been analysed qualitatively.

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2. Biswas and Palit, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 161.
3. Guha and Palit, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1963, Part A, **1**, 877.
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EXPERIMENTAL

Vinyl acetate, supplied by Eastman Kodak Company, Rochester, New York, was purified according to the procedure followed by Das and Palit⁴.

Analytical grade sodium hydrosulphite ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$) and potassium persulphate ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$), both supplied by E. Merck, were used as the redox components.

The polymerisation was carried out in a batch system^{1,2} under nitrogen at 35° in aqueous medium. The onset of polymerisation could be reckoned from the appearance of a certain haze in the initially clear solution. The monomer conversion to polymer was determined by a gravimetric procedure^{1,3}. The viscosities of the polymer samples were measured in acetone at $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. The coagulation values of the polymer latex in terms of the liminal strength of an aqueous solution of the electrolyte, sodium chloride, were determined by methods described elsewhere^{2,3}. These values were used as a measure of the dispersion stability of the polymer latex in aqueous medium. The solid content of the latex was kept constant (2%).

During typical experiments, polymerisations were conducted with (i) various ratios of the persulphate and hydrosulphite, keeping the concentration of the one fixed and varying that of the other; (ii) different concentrations of foreign electrolytes; (iii) various initial monomer concentrations; and (iv) at different temperatures.

Induction Period.—The time lag before the sudden appearance of a haze in the initially clear solution was reckoned as the induction period, t (sec.).

Fig. 1 shows a fairly linear dependence of $1/t$ (sec^{-1}) on the product of the concentration of the redox components, particularly at lower concentration range of the initiators.

Rate Dependence on Persulphate Concentration.—Fig. 2 shows a set of conversion-time plots where the persulphate concentration has been varied at

fixed monomer and reductant concentrations. At low persulphate concentrations, the yield-time plots are slightly sigmoidal. The initial acceleratory zone is gradually reduced on increasing the persulphate concentration with the attending start of the steady-rate zone. With still further increase of persulphate concentration, the acceleratory zone starts earlier and the yield-time plots at higher persulphate concentrations cross those at lower persulphate concentrations.

The above trend in rate is more clearly understood from Fig. 3 where the rate, averaged over a period of 30 min., has been plotted against persulphate concentrations. It follows that the rate initially rises with increasing persulphate concentration to a maximum and ultimately falls, exhibiting a tendency to rise again at a higher concentration of persulphate.

A similar behaviour of the rate was obtained in another case where the monomer and the hydrosulphite concentrations were kept at a lower level, viz., 0.05 m/l and 0.285×10^{-3} m/l respectively, whereas the persulphate concentration was varied from 1.11×10^{-3} m/l to 11.1×10^{-3} m/l.

Furthermore, the variation of the rate and the stability of the polymer sol is more or less parallel³ (Table I).

These features are more or less similar to those observed with other monomers in our previous studies¹⁻³.

Initiator Injection Experiment.—

Fig. 4 represents the yield-time plots for polymerisation in which an additional quantity of the persulphate is injected into the medium^{1-3,15} during the polymerisation, once near the beginning of a run and another at a later stage, (ca.) 15 min. after the start. The fresh addition of the catalyst near the beginning of the polymerisation enhances the rate.

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TABLE I

* Variation of rate and stability with catalyst concentration.

Catalyst ($K_2S_2O_8$) $\times 10^3$ m/l.	R_p (average over 30 min.) $\times 10^5$ m/l/s.	Coagulation value of latex (mm/l of NaCl, at 30 min.).
1.11	4.61	50
1.85	4.73	100
3.70	4.09	150
11.10	4.22	125
18.50	4.33	112

* All runs are with (vinyl acetate) = 0.104 m/l, ($Na_2S_2O_4$) = 0.58×10^{-3} m/l; temp. = 35°.

whereas the same during a run does not have any acceleratory effect, but, on the contrary, slightly depresses the rate.

Effect of Added Electrolytes on Polymerisation.—Fig. 5 reveals that sodium sulphate and magnesium sulphate depress the polymerisation rate^{1-3,13}.

Rate Dependence of Hydrosulphite Concentration.—Fig. 6 shows that polymerisation is continuously retarded as the hydrosulphite concentration is increased from 0.17×10^{-3} m/l to 1.70×10^{-3} m/l at fixed monomer and persulphate concentrations. At and above 2.86×10^{-3} m/l of hydrosulphite, the polymerisation is, however, almost completely inhibited. This behaviour is in definite contrast to the positive catalytic effect of the hydrosulphite observed earlier¹⁻³.

Rate Dependence on Monomer Concentration.—In Fig. 7, the average rate, computed over the first 30 min. of polymerisation, has been plotted against the initial concentration of monomer. The rate varies more or less linearly, but beyond 0.2 m/l monomer it tends to be decreased.

Rate Dependence on Temperature.—Fig. 8 shows that the overall rate of polymerisation increases with temperature up to 45° and falls with subsequent increase of temperature. Table II records the variation of initial rate and the limiting yield with temperature. The overall energy of activation is 9.4 kcal./m.

TABLE II

*Effect of temperature on rate.

Temp.	Initial R_p (m/l/s $\times 10^5$).	Limiting yield in 1hr (%).
20°	0.3	21.2
29°	3.3	71.9
35°	6.5	79.8
45°	10.5	85.0
55°	9.6	79.7

*All runs with monomer (vinyl acetate) = 0.052 m/l, $(K_2S_2O_8) = 1.85 \times 10^{-3}$ m/l, $(Na_2S_2O_4) = 0.285 \times 10^{-3}$ m/l.

Variation of $[\eta]$ with Rate and Catalyst Concentration.—Table III suggests that both the rate and intrinsic viscosity increase with the persulphate concentration to a maximum and subsequently fall with further increase of the latter. In a run $[\eta]$ increases with time¹⁻³.

FIG. 7

FIG. 8

TABLE III

* Variation of $[\eta]$ and rate with initiator concentration.

%K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ .	Average rate over 60 min. (%per min.).	$[\eta]$ (dl/g.).	
		30 min.	60 min.
0.03	1.22	..	0.90
0.05	1.30	1.20	1.20
0.06	1.15	0.90	1.00
0.08	1.18	0.60	0.80
0.10	1.28	0.62	0.78

*All runs with (vinyl acetate) = 0.5%, (Na₂S₂O₄) = 0.005% at 35°.

Vinyl Acetate and Acrylonitrile—A Comparative Study.—For comparing the effect of the nature of the monomeric entity on the rates of aqueous polymerisation, the yield-time graphs were obtained with the two monomers under almost identical conditions. Results are shown in Fig. 9. The coagulation values after 20 min. of polymerisation were measured to be 6.6 and 100 mm/l, NaCl, for polyacrylonitrile sol and the polyvinyl acetate sol respectively.

DISCUSSION

At low initiator concentration, polyvinyl acetate appears as a very stable suspension in aqueous medium. This stability may be ascribed to hydration and partly to the charge arising out of the adsorption of the dissolved ions in water. It may also originate from the adsorption of water-soluble oligomers containing sulphonate or sulphony end groups and behaving as anionic soaps¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Such highly stabilised systems, consisting of fine particles in large number, may develop^{2,3,12,15} the kinetic characteristics of a typical emulsion polymerisation. Accordingly, these systems can be treated from the point of view of the Smith-Ewart theory^{10,12}. Evidence^{1-4,15,16} also exists that the kinetics of such systems is somewhat dependent on the stability of the physical state of the latex. In the light of these views, the results of the present investigation can be justified as follows.

Rate Dependence on Catalyst and Coagulants.—Enhancement of the average rate (Fig. 3) with increasing catalyst concentration may be ascribed to the formation of a larger number of polymer particles acting as independent loci of polymerisation. Table I shows that the colloidal stability also tends to increase at first parallel to the rate. The subsequent fall in rate at increased catalyst concentration may be due to increasing degree of coagulation of the dispersed phase which provides the major polymerisation loci. The increase in the particle size, incident on this coagulation, may, however, permit simultaneous coexistence of more than one propagating radical in a latex particle. The situation then tends to assume the kinetic characteristics of model III of Smith and Ewart's theory¹⁰. The relatively high polymerisation rate at a very high catalyst concentration may, however, be due to the high viscosity of monomer-swollen polymer particles in which the bimolecular radical-termination rate is likely to become diffusion-controlled.

Electrolytes would tend to reduce the stability of the emulsions and consequently would diminish the number of particles while increasing their size. Hence the rate of the heterogeneous polymerisation will be retarded¹⁻³.

Initiator Injection Experiment.—It has been suggested by electron microscopic experiments¹² that in the persulphate-initiated emulsion-polymerisation of vinyl acetate, the maximum number of particles is produced at conversions (*ca.*) 16-20%. No new particles are formed thereafter while their size continues to increase. This indicates that the locus of polymerisation shifts almost quantitatively from the aqueous phase to the dispersed phase.

Motoyama¹¹, on the contrary, suggests that in the emulsion-polymerisation of vinyl acetate, new particles are formed even at about 80% conversion.

Our results seem to favour the usual picture. Thus the initiator added at the beginning of polymerisation, when the attainment of steady number of particles has not been complete, increases the rate of polymerisation. Added late in a run, the initiator has no effect on the rate; the slight fall in rate is ascribed to the incipient coagulation of the latex particles due to increase in the electrolyte concentration.

17. Bartlett and Nozaki, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1948, **3**, 216.

18. Willis, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1946, **41**, 2272.

19. Thomas, private communication.

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Rate Dependence on Hydrosulphite Concentration.—The anomalous behaviour of the reductant may be due to possible formation of some addition compounds with the monomer. This will result in lowering of the rate as well as in the yield of polymerisation. Similar interactions between various activators and monomers are known to occur²⁰.

A bromometric estimation of the free monomer in presence of the persulphate-hydrosulphite redox pair in a typical run showed the gradual fall in the monomer concentration without any visible polymerisation.

Incidentally, at a fixed monomer and persulphate concentration, there is an optimum hydrosulphite concentration, above which no visible polymerisation takes place. If the hydrosulphite be replaced by KHSO_3 , which is also known to form addition compounds²⁰, polymerisation takes place with decreasing rate at all concentrations of the latter in the range studied (*ca.*) 0.25×10^{-3} m/l to 8.3×10^{-3} m/l of KHSO_3 (monomer = 0.05 m/l and $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 1.11 \times 10^{-3}$ m/l). Probably the bisulphite forms a relatively loose addition compound with the monomer in which the polymerisation capacity of the latter is not severely impaired.

Pertinently, bubbling nitrogen through the solution containing monomer (0.05 m/l), $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (1.11×10^{-3} m/l), and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$ (above the optimum concentration) gives rise to considerable frothing. Probably the concentration of the monomer, available after side reaction with the reductant, is just enough to give rise to some water-soluble oligomers which perhaps cause the frothing¹⁹.

Rate Dependence on Monomer Concentration.—In an aqueous heterogeneous polymerisation, where the locus is distributed^{2,3,11} between the aqueous phase and the polymer particles, a satisfactory explanation of the monomer-dependence of rate presents a difficult issue. The observed dependence is likely to be the resultant of different concurrent processes, some taking place in the aqueous phase and some in the polymer particles. It has been noticed that the stability of the polymer particles decreases sharply as the monomer concentration increases. Similar observations have been also made with other monomers²¹⁻²³. It may be assumed tentatively that in the region of low-monomer concentrations, where the polymer particles appear as fine colloids of small size, the rate of monomer-transfer to the polymer particles turns out to be a slow process and hence rate-controlling. As the monomer concentration increases, the size of the particles increases as a result of the fall in stability, and consequently, the rate of monomer-transfer becomes a rapid process. This transition may account for the observed tendency of deviation from the linear course at higher concentrations of monomer.

Rate Dependence on Temperature.—It is felt that the decreasing stability of the colloidal polymer particles, as also the relative loss of initiator and monomer by side reactions at higher temperature, may explain the observed trend in the rate and the limiting yield.

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21. Biswas, D. Phil. thesis, Calcutta University, 1931.

22. Palit and Konar, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1962, 59, 85.

23. Guha, D. Phil. thesis, Calcutta University, 1961.

Comparison of Aqueous Polymerisation Behaviour of Acrylonitrile and Vinyl Acetate

Fig. 9 reveals that the overall rate of polymerisation and the limiting yield in the case of vinyl acetate remain at a higher level than those for acrylonitrile. This may be tentatively attributed to the following reasons. Thus, because of the much higher stability of polyvinyl acetate compared to that of polyacrylonitrile, the number of particles per ml of the polyvinyl acetate latex may perhaps be higher than that of the latter. A higher particle concentration should effect a higher rate. Moreover, unlike vinyl acetate, acrylonitrile does not have any affinity for its polymer. Consequently, the polymerisation of vinyl acetate may occur predominantly at the insoluble phase, whereas that of acrylonitrile may be overwhelmingly in the aqueous phase. The higher

FIG. 9

[VA]=[AN]=0.148 m/l.

[K₂S₂O₈]=2.59×10⁻³ m/l.

[Na₂S₂O₄]=0.59×10⁻³ m/l.

Temp.=35°.

viscosity of the monomer-soluble polymer particles in the former case possibly accounts for the higher rate of polymerisation.

The kinetic characteristics of the aqueous heterophase polymerisation of vinyl acetate are somewhat related to the stability of the physical state of the latex. Thus a higher rate of polymerisation may be identified with a more stable polymer sol. At low conversion, the stability of the latex remains high and the particle size is comparatively small. The locus of polymerisation has then a greater probability of being distributed in the aqueous phase and the dispersed phase. This process may further be facilitated by the hydrophilic nature of the monomeric radical and the probability of monomer-transfer of the polymeric radicals. At high conversion, however, the latex stability falls and the particle size increases. The reaction locus may predominate at the insoluble particles and in the limit, there may be more than one propagating radicals in a particle. Qualitatively, the former situation may be identified to case I and the latter to case III of the kinetic model of Smith and Ewart.

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